

**ANTI-CANCER ACTIVITY OF CLOVE OIL AGAINST MCF-7 CELL LINE
INDUCED BREAST CANCER AND Caco-2 CELL LINE INDUCED COLON
CANCER IN MICE**

AUTHOR: G.Pravalika

Department Of Pharmacology, Malla Reddy College of Pharmacy

Maisammaguda, Dhulapally, Secunderabad-500014

ABSTRACT:

Clove, the sun-dried unopened flower bud from the plant *Syzygium aromaticum* L. is a commonly used spice and food flavor. The oil of clove is rich in eugenol, carvacrol, and other phytochemical constituents. It also possesses flavonoids like kaempferol and eugenin. The major constituent eugenol being a monocyclic, oxygenated, aromatic monoterpene is expected to be a potent chemo-preventive and a therapeutic agent in cancer therapy. In the current study we have evaluated the anticancer potential of clove oil against Caco-2 induced colon cancer and MCF-7 induced breast cancer. Swiss mice were grouped into seven groups of which group 1 was normal control, group 2 & 3 were cancer control groups injected with Caco-2 and MCF-7 cell lines to induce colon and breast cancer respectively, group 4 & 5 were allotted for standard treatment and then group 6 & 7 were for Clove treatment. The treatment continued for four weeks and finally blood was collected by carotid puncture and sacrificed by ether anesthesia to evaluate various serum and tissue parameters. The therapeutic potential of clove is expected to be due to its monoterpene constituent eugenol. It was found that treatment of cell-line induced breast and colon cancer groups with clove oil has shown a significant effect on the carcino-embryonic antigen and other hematologic parameters. It showed a significant reduction of various serum biochemical parameters like SGPT, LDH, GGT, ALP and ferritin and increased the antioxidant levels. Thus, it was found that cloves have therapeutic potential as an anticancer agent.

INTRODUCTION: Volatile oils, also known as essential oils, are lipophilic compounds containing volatile aroma compounds. The constituents of the oils are mainly monoterpenes and sesquiterpenes which are hydrocarbons with the general formula $(C_5H_8)_n$. Oxygenated compounds derived from the hydrocarbons include alcohols, aldehydes, esters, ethers, ketones, phenols and oxides. It is estimated that there are more than 1000 monoterpene and 3000 sesquiterpene structures. Other compounds include phenylpropenes and specific

compounds containing sulphur or nitrogen. Hundreds of new natural substances are being isolated and identified every year, but data concerning their biological activities are known for only some. The volatile compounds of oils are aromatic or odoriferous that occurs in plants as such or less frequently may result from the degradation of glycerides by enzyme action. Medicinal uses proposed by sellers of essential oils vary from skin treatments to remedies for cancer

Cancer is a hyperproliferative disorder that involves transformation, dysregulation of apoptosis, proliferation, invasion, angiogenesis and metastasis. Extensive research during the last 30 years has revealed much about the biology of cancer. Normal body cells grow, divide, and die in an orderly fashion. If DNA damage occurs, it is repaired in most of the formation, the most relevant are those activating proto-oncogenes and inactivating tumour suppressor genes. Most cancers in humans are induced by carcinogenic factors present in our environment including our food.

Clove essential oil (*Syzygium aromaticus*):

Main active compound: Eugenol and eugenyle acetate

Properties: Antiviral, Antimicrobial, Antifungal, General stimulating, Hypertensive aphrodisiac, Light stomachic, Carminative, Anaesthetic

CELL LINES: -MCF-7 is a cell line that was first isolated in 1970 from the breast tissue of a 69-year-old Caucasian woman. Of the two mastectomies she received, the first revealed the removed tissue to be benign. Five years later, a second operation revealed malignant adenocarcinoma in a pleural effusion from which was taken cells for MCF-7. The woman was treated for breast cancer with radiotherapy and hormone-therapy.

Caco-2 cells are most commonly used not as individual cells, but as a confluent monolayer on a cell culture insert filter (e.g., Trans well). When cultured in this format, the cells differentiate to form a polarized epithelial cell monolayer that provides a physical and biochemical barrier to the passage of ions and small molecules. The Caco-2 monolayer is widely used across the pharmaceutical industry as an in vitro model of the

human small intestinal mucosa to predict the absorption of orally administered drugs. The correlation between the in vitro apparent permeability (Papp) across Caco-2 monolayers and the in vivo fraction absorbed (fa) is well established.

2

OBJECTIVES: Main objectives of this study are:

- **Phase 1:** To evaluate the Anticancer effect of Clove oil against MCF-7 Breast cancer and CACO-2 induced Colon cancer.
- **Phase 2:** Recording the difference in **Body weights** and **Abdominal circumference** of mice.
- **Phase 3:** To estimate the **Hematological parameters**.
- **Phase 4:** To estimate the **Serum parameters**.
- **Phase 5:** To estimate **Ferritin** and **CEA**
- **Phase 6:** To estimate **Tissue parameters**
- **Phase 7:** Histopathological studies

MATERIALS: -

EQUIPMENTS: Tissue Homogenizer, UV Visible Spectrophotometer, Cool Centrifuge, Digital Colorimeter, Deep refrigerator

CHEMICALS: - ALP kit, Acetic Acid, Catalase, CDNB, DTNB, Glutathione Reductase, Hcl, H₂O₂, K₂HPO₄, LDH kit, Methanol, Na₂HPO₄, NaOH, TBA, Phosphoric Acid, SPGT kit, Glucose kit, GGT kit, SLS, Sodium Citrate

CELL LINES: - MCF-7 Breast cancer cell lines, Caco2 colon cancer cell lines

METHODOLOGY: - Animals were grouped into 7 groups (Normal saline group common for both cancers) as explained above. The control group animals were given 0.9 % normal

saline 1ml for 30days. Group 2 animals were given MCF-7 cell line 2×10^6 cells/mouse I.P. Group 3 animals were given MCF-7 cell line 2×10^6 cells/mouse I.P and clove oil 500mg/kg p.o. until 30th day.

Group 4 animals were given MCF-7 cell line 2×10^6 cells/mouse I.P and 5-Flouro uracil 20mg/kg body weight I.P. until 30th day. Group 5 animals were given Caco2 cell line 2×10^6 cells/mouse I.P. Group 6 animals were given CACO-2 cell line 2×10^6 cells/mouse I.P. and clove oil 500mg/kg p.o until 30th day. Group 7 animals were given CACO-2 cell line 2×10^6 cells/mouse I.P. and 5-Flouro uracil 20mg/kg body weight I.P. until 30th day.

Blood sample preparation: The animals were sacrificed on 30th day using ether anaesthesia, blood was collected by carotid puncture method. Blood was collected and transferred to anticoagulant EDTA tubes for the estimation of haematological parameters like Hb, RBC and WBC.

Serum sample preparation: The animals were sacrificed on 30th day using ether anaesthesia, blood was collected by carotid puncture method. Blood was centrifuged using Remi cool centrifuge at 4000 rpm for 15 minutes. Serum was separated for the estimation of various biochemical parameters like serum SGPT, alkaline phosphatase, Ferritin, Carcano embryonic antigen, LDH, GGT and glucose.

Tissue sample preparation: At the end of the experiment, animals were sacrificed with light ether anaesthesia. Liver and kidney tissues were separated and washed with phosphate buffer saline (0.05M, P^H7.4). The liver and kidney later were taken and minced into small pieces and homogenized in ice cold phosphate buffer saline (0.05M, P^H7.4) using tissue homogenizer to obtain 1:9 (w/v) (10%) whole homogenate. A part of the liver and kidney homogenate was taken and mixed with equal volume of 10% Trichloroacetic acid (TCA) for the estimation of malondialdehyde. Homogenate was centrifuged using Remi cool centrifuge at 8000 rpm for 30 mins. The supernatant was separated and used for estimation of antioxidant levels of different enzymes i.e. Catalase and reduced glutathione, malondialdehyde and glutathione peroxidase in the tissues-liver.

Albino Mouse

Clove Buds

wiseGEEK

GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION:

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION :

Effect of Clove oil on Weights and Abdominal circumference: There was a significant increase in body weight and abdominal circumference of cell line induced mice i.e., in case of both Caco-2 (2.75 ± 0.25), (1.2 ± 0.05) and MCF-7 (5.50 ± 0.65), (1.10 ± 0.058) induced cancer control groups compared to normal control groups (Caco2- 1.25 ± 0.41 , 0.60 ± 0.06), (MCF-7- 2.25 ± 0.48 , 0.70 ± 0.05). Treatment with 5-FU and Clove oil significantly decreased the body weights and abdominal circumference at the end of the treatment.

Estimation of Haematological Data: Haemoglobin content and RBC count were significantly decreased in caco2 (13.40 ± 0.2), (6.80 ± 0.15)] induced colon cancer control group respectively and total WBC count was significantly increased (6.8 ± 0.15), compared to the normal control group (15.10 ± 0.10), (8.40 ± 0.20), (1.1 ± 0.08). Treatment with 5-FU and Clove oil significantly restored the haemoglobin and RBC and WBC levels towards the normal.

Estimation of Serum parameters: There was a significant increase in the serum parameters like SGPT, LDH, GGT, ALP in Caco2- (39.67 ± 1.4), (32.83 ± 1.24), (28.29 ± 1.26), (20.44 ± 1.19) induced colon cancer control compared to normal control (20.9 ± 0.98), (45.32 ± 0.83) (22.24 ± 1.26) (9.46 ± 0.24) respectively and treatment with 5-FU and Clove oil significantly decreased the Enzyme activity compared to Cancer control group

Estimation of Ferritin and CEA: The ferritin levels were significantly decreased in Caco2 control (66.40 ± 3.60) and MCF7 control (140.20 ± 5.60) compared to normal control (86.27 ± 4.80), (180.60 ± 6.44) respectively and were significantly increased after treatment with Clove oil.

There was a significant increase in CEA levels in Caco2 control (33.20 ± 1.12) and MCF7 control (24.80 ± 0.82) compared to normal control (5.80 ± 0.28), (6.10 ± 0.34) respectively and were significantly decreased after treatment with Clove oil.

Estimation of Tissue Anti-oxidant Parameters: There was a significant decrease in GSH and GPx levels in Caco2 induced control (7.57 ± 0.13), (4.23 ± 0.32) and MCF7 (7.12 ± 0.16), (5.23 ± 0.86) control respectively compared to normal control colon (14.67 ± 0.77), (7.87 ± 0.35) and breast (12.68 ± 0.77), (8.67 ± 0.68) and treatment with Clove oil significantly increased.

CONCLUSION: -

The present study was carried out to evaluate the anticancer activity of clove oil on Cell-line induced mice. The extract treatment at the dose of 500 mg/kg inhibited the increase in body weight and abdominal circumference and brought back the serum biochemical and haematological parameters towards normal levels. The extract also restored the free radical scavenging enzyme GSH as well as other antioxidant enzymes such as CAT and GPx in tumour bearing mice to near normal levels.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

The authors would like to thank the Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Mrs. V. UMARANI, M. Pharm., (Ph.D) and the laboratory staff for providing facilities and support to carry out this research work.

REFERENCES:

1. Derwich E., Benziane Z. and Boukir A., Chemical composition and antibacterial activity of leaves essential oil of *Laurus nobilis* from Morocco, *Aust. J. Basic Appl. Sci.*, 2009; 3(4):3818-3824.
2. Kose E.O., Akta et al, Chemical composition, antimicrobial and antioxidant activity of essential oil of endemic *Ferula lycia* Boiss, *J. Med. Plant. Res.*, 2010; 4(17): 1698-1703.
3. Pisutthanan N., Liawruangrath S., Bremner J.B. and Liawruangrath B., Chemical constituents and biological activities of *Chromolaena odorata*, *Chiang Mai J. Sci.*, 2005; 32(2): 139-148.
4. Cheng S.S., Wu C.L., Chang H.T., Kao Y.T. and Chang S.T., Antitermitic and antifungal activities of essential oil of *Calocedrus formosana* leaf and its composition, *J. Chem. Ecol.*, 2004; 30(10): 1957-1967.

5. Joy PP, Thomas J, Mathew S, Skaria BP. Medicinal Plants. Thesis. Ernakulum, Kerela: Kerela Agricultural University, 1998, p.1-211.
6. Rajesh D, Stenzel R, Howard S., Perillyl alcohol as a radio-chemosensitizer in malignant glioma. *J Biol Chem*,2003;278:35968-78.
7. Merle H, Morón M, Blázquez AM, Boira H. Taxonomical contribution of essential oils in mandarins cultivars. *Biochem Syst Ecol* 2004; 32:491-7.
8. Ahmad MM, Rehman SU, Iqbal Z, Anjum FM, Sultan JI. Genetic variability to essential oil. composition of four citrus species. *Pak J Bot* 2006;38:319-24.
9. Iwu WM, Duncan AR, Okunji CO. New antimicrobials of plant origin. In: Janick J, editor. *Perspectives on new crops and new uses*. Alexandria, VA, USA: ASHS Press; 1999. p. 457-62.
10. Bharat BA, Shishir S. Molecular targets of dietary agents for prevention and therapy of cancer. *Biochem Pharmacol* 2006;71:1397-421.
11. López S, Yolanda MP, Beatriz B, Rocío A, Francisco JG. Olive oil and cancer. *Int J Fats Oils* 2004;55:33-41.
12. The cell cycle. Image from Purves et al., *Life: The Science of Biology*, 4th Edition, by Sinauer Associates and WH Freeman.
13. American Cancer Society. *Breast Cancer Facts and Figures 2011-2012*. Atlanta, Ga: American Cancer Society; 2011.
14. American Cancer Society. *Cancer Facts and Figures 2013*. Atlanta, Ga: American Cancer Society; 2013.
15. da Rocha AB, Lopes RM, Schwartzmann G. Natural products in anticancer therapy. *Curr opin Pharmacol* 2001;1:364-9.

16. Schwartzmann G, Brondani da Rocha A, Berlinck RG, Jimeno J. Marine organisms as a source of new anticancer agents. *Lancet Oncol* 2001;2:221-5
17. Mans DR, da Rocha AB, Schwartzmann G. Anticancer drug discovery and development in Brazil: Targeted plant collection as a rational strategy to acquire candidate anti-cancer compounds. *Oncologist* 2000; 5:185-98.
18. Newman DJ, Cragg GM, Snader KM. The influence of natural products upon drug discovery. *Nat Prod Rep* 2000; 17:215-34.
19. Cragg GM, Newman DJ. Plants as a source of anti-cancer agents. *J Ethnopharmacol* 2005; 100:72-9.
20. C.P. Khare (Ed.), *Indian Medicinal Plants; An Illustrated Dictionary*, P.no. 636-637
21. Abdelouaheb Djilani and Amadou Dicko, *The Therapeutic Benefits of Essential Oils*. P.no.16
22. Osborne CK, Hobbs K, Trent JM: Biological differences among MCF-7 human breast cancer cell lines from different laboratories. *Breast Cancer Res Treat* 1987, 9:111-121.
23. Bahia H, Ashman JNE, Cawkwell L, Lind M, Monson JRT, and Drew PJ, Greenman J: Karyotypic variation between independently cultured strains of the cell line MCF-7 identified by multicolour fluorescence in situ hybridization. *Int J Oncol* 2002, 20:489-494.
24. Nelson-Rees WA, Daniels DW, Flandermeyer RR: Cross-contamination of cells in culture. *Science* 1981, 212: 446-452.
25. Gey GO, Coffman WD, Kubicek MT: Tissue culture studies of the proliferative capacity of cervical carcinoma and normal epithelium. *Cancer Res* 1952, 12:264-265.